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SHORT DESCRIPTION OF CONTENT: News Paper Articles and Reports and Conference material regarding legal reform in the GDR in the 1950s and 1960s.

PERSON VISITING ARCHIVE: Ville Erkkilä

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RESTRICTIONS OF USE: -

KEY WORDS: Legal history, GDR, Socialism, Authoritarian regimes

RELATES TO PUBLICATIONS: Ville Erkkilä & Luisa Gries. "‘The Problem Can Be Solved Only by Those Imbued with Socialist Sense of Justice’: Social Conflict and the Lower Courts in the German Democratic Republic". *Law and History Review* (2025), 1-23.